

Studies on Thiazolidinones. Part-XII : Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activities of Thiazolidinones and Their Derivatives from Cyclic Thioureas

S. N. DEHURI and A. NAYAK

Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University, Sambalpur-768 017

Manuscript received September 1981, revised 11 March 1983, accepted 1 September 1983

Syntheses of several new thiazolidinones (III ; $n=3-10$) and their hydrochlorides (IV ; $n=3-10$) have been achieved by reacting cyclic thioureas (II) with monochloroacetic acid and ethyl chloroacetate, respectively. The 2-arylidene derivatives of thiazolidinones (VI), synthesised by two different routes, gave thiazolidin-2,4-dione hydrochloride (IX) after hydrolysis with HCl. The bactericidal and fungicidal activities of the compounds have been evaluated.

IN continuation of our earlier work on thiazolidinones¹⁻³, several new thiazolidinones and their various derivatives have been synthesised from 2-mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (II ; $n=3$) and several other higher homologues (II ; $n=4-10$) by reacting with either monochloroacetic acid or ethyl chloroacetate with a view to evaluating their fungicidal and bactericidal activities against different microbes found in the soil and water of this locality.

The multi-step synthesis of 5,6-dihydroimidazo[2,1-b] thiazolidinone hydrochloride (IV ; $n=2$) was reported first by Campaigne *et al*⁴ by the reaction of 2-mercaptoimidazoline (II ; $n=2$) with either monochlorosodiumacetate or ethyl chloroacetate. The one-step synthesis of the same compound was also reported by Pujari *et al*⁵ by condensation with ethyl chloroacetate at higher temperature. Although the isolation of free base of this compound by several methods was unsuccessful, several of its higher homologues have been synthesised as hydrochlorides as well as free bases by us in the present study. Thus, reaction of 2-mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (II ; $n=3$) with monochloroacetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate furnished 6,7-dihydro-5H-thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidin-3(2H)-one (III ; $n=3$) as pale yellow solid. When the reaction was carried out by refluxing a mixture of tetrahydropyrimidine and ethyl chloroacetate, the hydrochloride (IV ; $n=3$) of the compound was isolated as brown crystals from which free base was obtained after neutralising with K_2CO_3 solution. Similarly, compound (IV ; $n=3$), when condensed with benzaldehyde in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid furnished arylidene derivatives (VI ; $n=3$), which was also obtained directly by reacting a mixture of II ($n=3$), ethyl chloroacetate and benzaldehyde in the presence of piperidine in ethanol. Although Pujari *et al*⁵

isolated the thiazolidin-2,4-dione hydrochloride derivatives by reacting ethylenethiourea with ethyl

- $n=3-10$; X = -Br or -NH₂
- (X = NH₂), CS₂, EtOH,
 - (X = Br), NH₂ - CS - NH₂, EtOH, RCHO, and piperidine,
 - Cl - CH₂ - COOH, NaOAc, EtOH,
 - Cl - CH₂ - COEt,
 - RCHO, NaOAc, HOAc,
 - Cl - CH₂ - COOEt, pyridine,
 - Conc. HCl,
 - Cl - CH₂ - COOH, H₂O,
 - Br₂ in CHCl₃.

chloroacetate at 140° or monochloroacetic acid in water, the reaction with higher homologues did not yield such products. On the other hand, the arylidene derivatives (VI) furnished the thiazolidin-2,4-dione hydrochloride (IX) after hydrolysis with conc. HCl. The authenticity of these compounds, prepa-

red by separate methods, was confirmed by m.m.p. and spectral studies. The ^1H nmr spectra of the thiazolidinone III ($n=3$) showed a sharp singlet at δ 4.10 and a complex multiplet centered at δ 2.15 corresponding to two and six protons present in the methylene groups of thiazole and pyrimidine ring, respectively. On the other hand its benzylidene derivative (VI; $n=3$) showed six proton multiplet at δ 2.1, one proton singlet at δ 6.3, and another five proton multiplet centered at δ 7.5 corresponding to methin, methylene and aromatic protons, respectively.

The higher homologues of tetrahydropyrimidine (II; $n=4-10$) were prepared by condensing respective aliphatic dibromides with thiourea in alcohol. The possibility of the formation of the compounds of the type X was ruled out as the products are soluble in alkali and no reaction occurred with phenylisothiocyanate. In some cases these were isolated as hydrobromides (V; $n=4-10$) from which the free bases (II; $n=4-10$) were obtained after neutralisation with K_2CO_3 .

The reactions of the higher homologues of thioureas with ethyl chloroacetate were not smooth and yields were not high as compared to the yields of the usual chloroacetic acid method. Similarly, low yields were observed in the direct arylidene derivatives synthesised from thioureas.

As the introduction of bromine⁷ and sulphonamido moiety⁸ into the heterocyclic ring increases their antimicrobial activities, dibromides (VIII) from IV and sulphonamido derivatives (VII) from III have also been prepared. Though the dibromo derivatives obtained from the benzylidene compounds possess two chiral centres, the resolution of the isomers was difficult. The structures of these compounds were also confirmed from spectral data. Thus, the 6,7-dihydro-2-bromo-2-(α -bromobenzyl)-5H-thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3(2H)-one (VIII; $n=3$, $\text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$) gave a strong band at 1740 cm^{-1} for carbonyl group whereas its benzylidene derivative (VI; $n=3$, $\text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) gave the same carbonyl absorption at 1695 cm^{-1} . The hypsochromic shift is due to the removal of unsaturation which was in conjugation with the carbonyl. Similarly, the nmr of the dibromo compound gave a one proton singlet at δ 3.2 which appeared at δ 6.1 in the benzylidene derivative. The upfield shift in the benzylic proton absorption is due to the saturation of the double bond.

Antimicrobial activities: Using agar plate diffusion technique, the newly synthesised thiazolidinones and their derivatives were tested *in vitro* for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis* and *B. pumilus*. The results indicate that all the compounds exhibit antibacterial activity against one or the other bacteria. The activity decreases with increase in ring size. Similar pattern was observed in case of antifungal activities of the compounds against *A. niger*, *A. nidlans* and *C. albican* on Sabouraud's broth medium.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir of the compounds were recorded in Perkin Elmer, Model 293 spectrophotometer. The nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 solution with TMS as internal standard on Varian HA-60 spectrometer.

6,7-Dihydro-5H-thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidin-3(2H)-one (III; $n=3$):

Method A: 2-Mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (1.16 g), monochloroacetic acid (1.42 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g) in ethanol was refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr with occasional shaking. The solvent was distilled off and the residue triturated with water and filtered. The residue after recrystallisation from ethanol furnished a pale yellow solid, m.p. 201° , yield 0.8 g (50%). (Found: C, 46.03; H, 5.10; N, 17.82; S, 20.51. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{SO}$ requires C, 46.15; H, 5.13; N, 17.95; S, 20.39%). $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm^{-1}): 2900 (C-H stretching in CH_2), 1730 (C=O), 1585 (C=N). NMR δ : 2.15 [m, $(-\text{CH}_2)_2$, 6H], 4.15 (s, $-\text{CH}_2$, 2H).

Method B: 2-Mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (5.8 g; 0.05 mole) and ethyl chloroacetate (30 ml; 0.5 mole) were heated on an oil bath for 6 hr during which a dark brown solid appeared. It was dissolved in ethanol and the solution treated with animal charcoal and filtered hot. The solution was concentrated when brown crystals of the hydrochloride (IV; $n=3$) of the above compound separated, m.p. 261° (decomp), yield 3.35 g (35%). (Found: S, 16.69. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{SOCl}$ requires S, 16.93%).

The free base (III; $n=3$) was obtained after dissolving the salt in water and neutralising the solution with K_2CO_3 solution as pale yellow solid, m.p. 201° (m.m.p. undepressed).

6,7-Dihydro-2-benzylidene-5H-thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3(2H) one (VI; $n=3$, $\text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$):

Method A: Compound III ($n=3$) (1.92 g; 0.01 mole) and benzaldehyde (1.06 g; 0.01 mole) in ethanol (15 ml) and piperidine (2 drops) was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. After cooling it was poured onto crushed ice and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 150° , yield 0.95 g (65%). (Found: C, 63.85; H, 4.91; N, 11.36; S, 13.01. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{SO}$ requires C, 63.93; H, 4.92; N, 11.47; S, 13.11%). $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm^{-1}): 2910 (C-H stretching), 1695 (C=O), 1600 (C=N stretching). NMR δ : 2.1 [m, $(-\text{CH}_2)_2$, 6H], 6.3 (s, $-\text{CH}=\text{}$, 1H), 7.5 (m, aromatic protons).

Method B: A mixture of II ($n=3$) (1.16 g; 0.01 mole), ethyl chloroacetate (1.25 g; 0.01 mole) in ethanol (20 ml) and pyridine (2 drops) was refluxed for 8 hr during which a dark coloured solution was obtained. To this, benzaldehyde (1.16 g) and two drops of piperidine were added. The mixture was refluxed for another 1 hr and kept overnight during which orange needles separated, m.p. 150° (m.m.p. undepressed), yield 0.5 (40%).

6,7-Dihydro-2-bromo-2-(α -bromobenzyl)-5H-thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3(2H)-one (VIII; n=3, R=C₆H₅): Benzylidenethiazolidinone (0.5 g) in chloroform (20 ml) was treated with bromine (0.5 g) in chloroform at 10° for 10 min. It was kept in the refrigerator overnight and the solvent removed. The residue was suspended in water and SO₂ gas was passed till it went into solution. The solution was filtered and the filtrate basified with ammonia which gave an orange residue. It was recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 185°, yield 40%. (Found: C, 38.48; H, 2.84; N, 6.80; Br, 39.71. C₁₃H₁₂N₂SOBr₂ requires C, 38.61; H, 2.97; N, 6.93; Br, 39.60%). ν_{max}^{KBr} (cm⁻¹): 2900 (C-H stretch), 1740 (C=O), 1600 (C=N). NMR δ : 2.05 [m, -(CH₂)₂-, 6H], 3.2 (s, -CH=, 1H), 7.45 (m, 5-aromatic protons).

1-H-2-Mercapto-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro [1,3] diazepine (II; n=4): A mixture of 1,4-dibromobutane and thiourea (3.8 g) in ethanol was refluxed on water bath for 12 hr. The solvent was removed and the residue triturated with water and kept overnight. It was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol as white needles, m.p. 213° (lit° m.p. 213°), yield 45%.

4,5,6,7-Tetrahydro-4H-diazepino[2,1-b]thiazol-3(2H)-one (III; n=4):

Method A: This was prepared in 50% yield from mercaptotetrahydrodiazepine (1.30 g) and monochloroacetic acid (1.42 g) by following the general procedure, m.p. 219°. (Found: S, 18.75. C₇H₁₀N₂SO requires S, 18.82%). ν_{max}^{KBr} (cm⁻¹): 2940 (-CH- stretching), 1750 (C=O), 1600 (C=N).

Method B: A mixture of 2-mercaptodiazepine (1.30 g) and ethyl chloroacetate (30 ml) was heated on an oil bath for 8 hr. The dark solid was treated with norite and extracted with hot ethanol. The solvent was concentrated during which brown crystals of the hydrochloride (VI; n=4) separated, m.p. 270°, yield 0.62 g, (30%). (Found: S, 15.43. C₇H₁₁N₂SOCl requires S, 15.49%).

The free base (III; n=4) was isolated by neutralising in aqueous solution with K₂CO₃ solution and was recrystallised from alcohol as colourless needles, m.m.p. 219°. (Found: S, 18.62. C₇H₁₀N₂SO requires S, 18.82%).

2-Benzylidene-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-4H-diazepino[2,1-b]thiazol-3(2H)-one (VI; n=4; R=C₆H₅):

Method A: This was prepared by refluxing a mixture of III (n=4) (1.7 g), benzaldehyde (1.06 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (40 ml) for 4 hr and pouring the resulting solution onto crushed ice. The yellow solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol as needles, m.p. 187°, yield 50%. (Found: S, 12.31. C₁₄H₁₄N₂SO requires S, 12.40%). ν_{max}^{KBr} (cm⁻¹): 2950 (-CH- stretching), 1720 (C=O), 1585 (C=N).

Method B: A mixture of mercaptotetrahydrodiazepine (1.30 g), ethyl chloroacetate (1.25 g) in ethanol (10 ml) and 2 drops of pyridine was refluxed for 8 hr. The resulting bright yellow solution was further refluxed for 3 hr after adding benzaldehyde (0.1 g) and a few drops of piperidine, and kept overnight during which orange needles

TABLE I

n	Thioureas (II)*			Thiazolidinones(III)**			BS [†]	CA [†]	Sulphonamido derivatives (VII)				
	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	% Sulphur Found (Calcd.)	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	% Sulphur Found (Calcd.)			m.p. °C	Mol. formula	% Nitrogen Found (Calcd.)	BS	CA
3	-	-	-	-	-	-	2+	50	-	-	-	2+	25
4	-	-	-	-	-	-	2+	25	168	-	19.62 (19.83)	3+	50
5	208	C ₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	22.14 (22.22)	198	C ₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ SO	17.21 (17.39)	2+	50	197	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	-	2+	50
6	185	C ₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	20.09 (20.25)	207	C ₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO	16.03 (17.16)	+	100	216	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	-	+	-
7	149*	C ₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ S	18.38 (18.60)	216	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ SO	15.12 (15.09)	+	-	207	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	15.31 (15.18)	+	-
8	151*	C ₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ S	17.15 (17.20)	231	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ SO	14.10 (14.15)	+	-	>250	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	-	-	-
9	136*	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ S	16.06 (16.00)	228	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ SO	13.18 (13.33)	-	-	>250	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	-	-	-
10	130*	C ₁₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ S	14.83 (14.95)	246	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₂ SO	12.46 (12.59)	-	-	250	C ₁₇ H ₂₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	-	-	-

[†]BS - *B. subtilis*, CA - *C. albicans*; + - zone size 6-8 mm; 2+ - zone size 9-14 mm; 3+ - zone size 15-20 mm; - - inactive.

* Thioureas were isolated after neutralising the hydrochlorides with K₂CO₃ solution and the yields varies from 60-40%.

** The thiazolidinone hydrochlorides (IV) prepared by method B decomposed above 250° and the melting points of the free bases undepressed. Yields are less as compared to reported ones.

*** The number indicate minimum inhibitory concentration in μ g/ml. % yield of thiourea, thiazolidinones and sulphonamido derivatives varies from 30-45, 40-45 and 40-50, respectively.

TABLE 2

n	R	Arylidene-thiazolidinones (VI)			BS	CA***	Dibromides (VIII)		BS	CA***
		m.p. °C	Mol. formula	% Sulphur Found (Calcd.)			m.p. °C	% Bromine Found (Calcd.)		
3	Phenyl	-	-	-	2+	-	-	-	2+	-
	Thienyl-2	137	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ O	25.42 (25.60)	2+	100	174	38.83 (39.02)	3+	100
	Furyl-2	167	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ SO ₂	13.50 (13.67)	2+	50	186	42.08 (40.60)	2+	-
	p-Anisyl	176	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO ₂	11.48 (11.67)	-	-	205	36.59 (36.86)	-	-
4	phenyl	187	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO	12.31 (12.40)	+	-	214	38.12 (38.27)	3+	25
	Thienyl-2	165	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂ O	24.10 (24.24)	2+	50	198	37.64 (37.73)	2+	25
	Furyl-2	191	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ SO ₂	12.81 (12.90)	+	50	175	37.17 (37.21)	2+	100
	p-Anisyl	167	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO ₂	11.20 (11.11)	-	-	201	35.65 (35.71)	-	-
5	Phenyl	210	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO	11.50 (11.76)	2+	-	235	37.05 (37.03)	2+	-
	Thienyl-2	196	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ O	22.87 (23.02)	2+	-	212	36.46 (36.52)	-	-
6	Phenyl	232	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO	11.06 (11.18)	+	-	>250	35.75 (35.87)	+	-
	Thienyl-2	246	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O	21.68 (21.91)	+	100	226	35.38 (35.39)	+	100
7	Phenyl*	216	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ SO	10.54 (10.66)	+	-	>250	34.70 (34.78)	-	-
	Thienyl-2*	210	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O	20.73 (20.91)	2+	-	217	34.16 (34.33)	+	-
	Furyl-2*	234	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO ₂	11.00 (11.03)	+	-	236	35.48 (35.55)	-	-
8	Phenyl*	233	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ SO	10.16 (10.19)	-	-	>250	34.36 (34.48)	-	-
9	Phenyl*	249	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ N ₂ SO	9.52 (9.73)	-	-	>250	31.65 (31.87)	-	-
10	Phenyl*	250	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ SO	9.21 (9.35)	-	-	>250	31.65 (31.87)	-	-
	Thienyl-2*	246	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O	18.16 (18.39)	-	-	244	31.33 (31.49)	-	-
	Furyl-2	218	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ SO ₂	9.50 (9.63)	-	-	240	40.72 (40.81)	-	-

* Recrystallised from DMF.

** The % yield varies from 45 to 60 and the % of yield is less when these were prepared by Method B. Antimicrobial activities against one bacteria and one fungi have been shown.

BS = *B. subtilis*, CA = *C. albicans*; + = zone size 6-8 mm, 2+ = zone size 9-14 mm, 3+ = zone size 15-20 mm, - = inactive.

*** The number indicates minimum inhibitory concentration in µg/ml.

separated, m.p. 187° (m.m.p. 187°), yield 45%. (Found: S, 12.31. C₁₄H₁₄N₂SO requires S, 12.40%).

3-(γ -Aminopropyl)-5-benzylidene thiazolidin-2,4-dione hydrochloride (IX; n=3): 6,7-Dihydro-2-benzylidene-5H-thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3(2H)-one (0.61 g) in 6N HCl (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 3 hr. Pale yellow solids separated on cooling. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 265° (d). (Found: S, 10.56. C₁₅H₁₅N₂O₂SCl requires S, 10.72%).

Bromination of VI to VIII: Arylidene thiazolidinones (VI; n=4-10) (0.5 g) in chloroform (20 ml) was treated with bromine (0.5 g) in chloroform (10 ml) at 10° for 10 min. It was kept in the refrigerator overnight and the solvent removed at room temp. The residue was suspended in water

and SO₂ gas was passed till it went into the solution. It was filtered and the filtrate basified with ammonia to furnish orange precipitates of the dibromides, which were recrystallised from acetic acid.

2-Sulphonamidophenylazo-6,7-dihydro-5H-thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3(2H)-one (VII; n=3): Sulphanilamide (0.5 g) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (1 ml) and water (25 ml) was diazotized with NaNO₂ (0.25 g) in water (30 ml) in an ice bath. The resulting diazo solution was added gradually with stirring to a previously cooled solution of thiazolidinone (0.45 g) in NaOH (5 g in 20 ml water) and kept in an ice bath. After addition, the mixture was stirred for another 0.5 hr during which yellow azo dye was separated. It was filtered and recryst-

tallised from ethanol, m.p. 120°. (Found : S, 18.84 ; N, 20.59. $C_{12}H_{12}N_2S_2O_2$ requires S, 18.91 ; N, 20.70%).

The analytical data and antimicrobial test results of various thioureas, thiazolidinones and sulpho-namido derivatives, arylidenethiazolidinones and their dibromides have been presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (S.N.D.).

References

1. G. R. NEWKOME and A. NAYAK, "Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry", (Ed.) A. R. KATRITZKY and A. J. BOULTON, Academic Press, 1979, Vol. 25, p. 83.
2. R. K. BEHERA and A. NAYAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **18B**, 141.
3. S. S. MEHER, S. NAYAK, R. K. BEHERA and A. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 274.
4. E. CAMPAIGNE and M. C. WANI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **19**, 1715.
5. H. S. CHOUDHURI and H. K. PUJARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 710.
6. V. K. CHADHA, H. S. CHOUDHURY and H. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 885.
7. G. N. MOHAPATRA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 988.
8. H. C. MUTREJA, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16B**, 519.